

Kinetics of Chromic Acid Oxidation of Phenacyl Bromides (*o*-Bromoacetophenones)

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The kinetics of the oxidation of phenacyl bromide (*o*-bromoacetophenone) and several substituted phenacyl bromides by chromic acid have been investigated in 90% acetic acid (v/v). The reaction rate is first order with respect to the [oxidant] as well as to the [substrate]. A decrease in the proportion of acetic acid in the reaction mixture decreases the rate. The reaction rate decreases in the presence of added Mn(II) ions. The presence of complexing agents like succinic acid and piperidine also decrease the rate. The value of ρ^* has been found to be -0.20 from a linear correlation of the rate constants with Brown's σ^+ parameter. The data conform to the mechanism involving an enol intermediate.

CHROMIC acid is one of the most versatile oxidising agents¹. Kinetics of oxidation of many alicyclic and aliphatic ketones by chromic acid have been reported by a number of workers²⁻⁵. Similar studies on α -haloketones are not found in the literature. This prompted us to study the kinetics of oxidation of phenacyl bromide and substituted phenacyl bromides to obtain more informations on the mechanism of oxidation.

Experimental

Materials and method: The substrates employed were unsubstituted, *p*-methoxy, *p*-methyl, *m*-nitro and *p*-nitro phenacyl bromide. These were prepared and purified by the methods available in literature⁶⁻⁷. Perchloric acid (60% Baker, AnalaR) was used as a source of H⁺. Pure acetic acid (b.p. 118°), free from oxidisable impurities, was obtained by warming acetic acid (AnalaR, 40 g) and acetic anhydride (AnalaR, 160 ml) slowly to just below the reflux temperature for 0.5 hr, the mixture was then heated under reflux for 0.5 hr and then distilled through a fractionating column containing glass helices. The ionic strength was maintained by adding sodium perchlorate (AnalaR, B.D.H). Triple distilled water was used for dilution.

Kinetic measurements: Rate measurements were carried out at constant temperature ($\pm 0.1^\circ$). The solvent used was 90% aqueous acetic acid (v/v) containing 0.2 M HClO₄. The reaction was followed by withdrawing aliquots of the reaction mixture at known intervals of time, quenching the reaction by adding slight excess of ferrous ammonium sulphate and titrating the residual Fe(II) against standard K₂Cr₂O₇ solution using barium diphenyl sulphate as an indicator. Diffused light did not affect the rate constants. The rate constants were computed with an accuracy of 1-2% in duplicate runs.

Stoichiometry: The stoichiometry of the reaction was determined by allowing reaction mixtures containing excess of chromic acid to stand for 3 to 4 days at 30° until there was no change of Cr(VI) concentration. The unreacted oxidant was then estimated by the usual procedure. The stoichiometry is represented by equation (1).

The tlc pure product isolated was characterised as phenyl glyoxal⁸, yellow liquid, b.p. 96°.

Rate law: The reaction is first order with respect to the [phenacyl bromide] as well as the [oxidant] (Table 1). The rate of the reaction increases with the increase in [HClO₄] (Table 2). Under the condition of constant ionic strength the first order rate constant (k_1) is proportional to [H⁺].

TABLE 1—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON [CrO₃] AND [*m*-NITRO PHENACYL BROMIDE]
[HClO₄] = 0.2 M, $\mu = 1$ M, Solvent = 90% Acetic acid (v/v),
Temp = 35°

[<i>m</i> -Nitrophenacyl bromide] × 10 ³ M	[CrO ₃] × 10 ⁴ M	$k_1 \times 10^5$ sec ⁻¹	$k_1 \times 10^5$ mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹
			[<i>m</i> -Nitrophenacyl bromide]
10.0	1.0	8.17	
10.0	2.0	4.50	
10.0	4.0	5.80	
10.0	5.0	7.90	
10.0	10.0	8.82	
10.0	15.0	8.40	
10.0	20.0	8.65	
10.0	25.0	8.70	
10.0	30.0	8.75	
10.0	10.0	4.20	8.40
5.0	10.0	8.82	8.82
10.0	10.0	16.90	8.45
20.0	10.0	24.80	8.26
30.0	10.0	33.10	8.27
40.0	10.0	42.20	8.27
50.0	10.0		

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TABLE 2—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON [ACID]

[CrO₃]=0.001 M ; [*m*-Nitro phenacyl bromide]=0.01 M ;
Solvent=90% Acetic acid (v/v) ; μ=1 M ; Temp.=35°

[HClO ₄], M	k ₁ × 10 ³ sec ⁻¹	k ₁ /[H ⁺] × 10 ⁴
0.1	4.25	0.425
0.2	8.82	0.441
0.3	13.02	0.434
0.4	17.28	0.432
0.5	21.46	0.429
0.6	25.90	0.447
0.7	28.45	0.441
0.8	33.76	0.442
0.9	40.30	0.447

Solvent effect: The reaction was studied in various acetic acid-water binary mixtures. An increase in the proportion of acetic acid increases the rate of oxidation (Table 3). This is probably due to the lowering of dielectric constant (D) of the medium⁹, which favours reaction involving protonation. In acetic acid medium, H₂CrO₄ exists as acetochromic acid, CH₃COOCrO₂H, or its protonated form CH₃COOCrO₂H₂⁺ which are assumed to be strong acids and much more powerful oxidising agents than chromic acid¹⁰⁻¹². The plot of log k₁ versus 1/D is linear as expected for ion-dipole reactions. The same argument has also been advanced by Venkatasubramanian¹³. Further, the extent of enolization of the ketone is enhanced by increasing the proportion of acetic acid and hence the rate increases.

Effect of added Mn(II): The reaction rate decreases in the presence of added Mn(II) ions (Table 4). The same observation has been noted

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF SOLVENT COMPOSITION ON THE RATE OF CHROMIC ACID OXIDATION OF PHENACYL BROMIDE

[CrO₃]=0.001 M ; [*m*-Nitro phenacyl bromide]=0.01 M ;
[HClO₄]=0.4 M ; μ=1 M ; Temp.=35°

%HOAc (v/v)	k ₁ × 10 ³ sec ⁻¹
70	4.79
75	5.02
80	6.90
85	8.05
90	17.28
95	20.72

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF Mn(II) IONS ON THE RATE OF OXIDATION OF PHENACYL BROMIDE

[CrO₃]=0.001 M ; [*m*-Nitro phenacyl bromide]=0.01 M ;
[HClO₄]=0.4 M ; Solvent=90% Acetic acid (v/v) ; Temp.=35°

[Mn(II)] × 10 ³ M	k ₁ × 10 ³ sec ⁻¹
—	17.28
10	3.50
15	2.25
20	1.80
25	0.90

by Westheimer and Watanabe¹⁴ for isopropanol oxidation. This is probably due to the Mn(II) catalysed disproportionation of intermediate valence states of [Cr(IV)]. It may be reasonable

to propose the following reaction in the presence of Mn(II) ions.

Effect of complexing agent on reaction rate:

The rate of the reaction decreases in the presence of certain dibasic acids and organic bases (Table 5). This may be due to complex forming ability of intermediate stages of the oxidant.

Effect of substituents on rate: The effect of substituents on the benzene ring of phenacyl bromide shows that electron donating groups enhance the reaction rate while electron withdrawing groups retard it (Table 6). The order of reactivity of different substituents is *p*-OCH₃ > *p*-CH₃ > H > *m*-NO₂ > *p*-NO₂. The log k₁ values for different substituted phenacyl bromides have been plotted against Brown's σ⁺ values¹⁵. The value of ρ⁺ was computed to be -0.20.

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF ADDED COMPLEXING AGENTS ON THE REACTION RATE

[CrO₃]=0.001 M ; [*m*-Nitro phenacyl bromide]=0.01 M ;
[HClO₄]=0.4 M ; Solvent=90% Acetic acid (v/v) ;
[Complexing agent]=0.01 M ; Temp.=35°

Complexing agent	k ₁ × 10 ³ sec ⁻¹
Nil	17.28
Succinic acid	5.60
Adipic acid	4.50
Piperidine	5.05
Pyridine	4.02
Diethylamine	3.30

TABLE 6—REACTION RATES AND ARRHENIUS PARAMETERS FOR CHROMIC ACID OXIDATION OF SUBSTITUTED PHENACYL BROMIDES

[CrO₃]=0.001 M ; [Substrate]=0.01 M ; [HClO₄]=0.2 M ;
μ=1 M ; Solvent=90% Acetic acid (v/v)

Substituent	k × 10 ³ sec ⁻¹ at °C			E k.cal/mole	-ΔS* e.u.
	30	35	40		
<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	9.21	13.05	17.25	11.52	40.89
<i>p</i> -CH ₃	8.20	12.02	16.15	12.46	38.08
H	7.60	10.80	13.55	13.12	36.03
<i>m</i> -nitro	5.44	8.82	12.80	15.36	33.59
<i>p</i> -nitro	4.44	7.75	10.85	17.06	24.04

Isokinetic relationship: A linear relationship between the entropy of activation (ΔS*) and the enthalpy of activation (ΔH*) has been observed for the oxidation¹⁶. The data can be fitted in the equation,

$$\Delta H^* = \Delta H_0^* + \beta \Delta S^*$$

ΔH₀^{*} has the value 25.5 kcal mole⁻¹ and β, the isokinetic temperature, is 381K for the reaction. The linear relationship shown by the majority of phenacyl bromides indicates that apparently the same mechanism prevails in all cases¹⁷.

Discussion

The aliphatic haloketones undergo hydrolysis in acid and alkaline medium. But phenacyl bromides are found to resist hydrolysis even upto an acid concentration of 0.9 M HClO₄.

The oxidation of phenacyl bromides by H_2CrO_4 shows that, (i) the oxidation rate is first order with respect to the haloketone, (ii) the rate at which Cr(VI) disappears also follows first order rate laws, (iii) the reaction is acid catalysed and (iv) the value of ρ^+ is negative showing that electron donating groups enhance the reaction rate. The value of $\Delta S^\ddagger$ is negative indicating a rigid transition state.

The formation of free radicals was not indicated in the present investigation since polymerization with acrylonitrile or reduction of $HgCl_2$ could not be observed. Therefore the oxidation reaction is believed to proceed through an ionic intermediate.

As pointed out by Best *et al.*², the rate of chromic acid oxidation of cyclohexanone by chromic acid is slower than its rate of enolization at the same acidity. Thus one cannot say whether the ketone molecule or its enol form is being attacked by the chromic acid. However, Rocek and Riche³ have advanced different views which contradict the views suggested by Best *et al.*². The latter workers observed that the rate of oxidation is close to the enolization as determined by bromination measurement, demonstrating that the oxidation of ketones proceeds through the enol intermediate. Nayak *et al.*¹⁸ have studied the bromination of a large number of acetophenones. The present experimental condition is very much close to the bromination experiment. Various substituents change the rate in the same direction in both the reactions as evidenced by the magnitude and size of the Hammett ρ value. Thus it seems likely that the oxidation proceeds through an enol intermediate. This receives support from the DMSO oxidation of phenacyl bromide¹⁶ and SeO_2 oxidation of a number of ketones²⁰.

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